

Utilization of Accounting Skills for Fixed Assets Management in Public Universities in Bayelsa State.

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Abstract

This study examined the utilization of accounting skills for fixed assets management in public universities in Bayelsa State. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population for the study comprised 102 (37 males and 65 female accountants) in public universities. There was no sampling because of the population's manageable size. The instrument used for data collection was a Google form structured questionnaire developed by the researcher titled "Utilization of Accounting Skills for Fixed Assets Management Questionnaire (UASFAMQ)". The instrument was validated by three research specialists. The reliability estimate was computed using Cronbach Alpha statistic which yielded 0.78 and 0.81 for clusters 1 and 2 with a reliability index of 0.80 making the instrument reliable. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the null hypotheses were tested using t-test statistic at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that depreciation methods and assets valuation and impairment testing techniques were utilized to a low extent for fixed assets management in public universities. It was recommended among others that University management should organize regular training and capacity-building workshops for asset managers and finance officers in public universities to enhance their knowledge and skills in the use of modern depreciation methods, asset valuation, and impairment testing techniques. This will improve the accuracy of fixed asset management and financial reporting.

Keywords: Utilization, Accounting Skills, Fixed Assets Management, Public Universities

Introduction

In today's competitive business environment, the efficient management of organizational resources has become a cornerstone for success. Organizations must harness specialized skills and competencies to optimize performance and drive growth. The strategic application of accounting practices plays a significant role in this process, ensuring that resources are utilized effectively and financial decisions are well-informed. As educational institutions and public entities face unique challenges, the importance of integrating advanced accounting techniques into resource management becomes increasingly evident.

Effectively managing organizational resources is crucial for achieving profitability and growth. This process necessitates the application of specialized competencies, proficiency, and skills to ensure optimal performance and efficiency. Amesi and Babalola (2022) emphasized that these competencies, which include accounting skills, should be developed during school years and further enhanced post-graduation. Adequate accounting knowledge and methods are vital for sound financial management, judgment, and shaping an organization's identity. Aja (2018) noted

that business education students can acquire accounting skills, which include tasks such as preparing accounting data from vouchers and cash books, managing wages and salaries, and creating daily or monthly statements of accounts. These skills, whether traditional or modern, include various approaches, guidelines, and procedures essential for handling financial transactions and assessing financial data for different users.

Applying relevant accounting knowledge is crucial in managing resources in public entities, particularly for public universities in Bayelsa State, the focus of this research. Effective management of fixed assets is emphasized, with Ashmarina and Zotova (2015) describing fixed assets as tangible resources with a long-term utility in producing or selling products or services, which cannot be quickly converted into cash. Enekwe (2018) categorized fixed assets into tangible and intangible types, noting that these are long-term investments with a lifespan exceeding one year. Tangible assets include land, buildings, and machinery, while intangible assets comprise goodwill, patents, and trademarks.

Scholars have pointed out that tertiary institutions using a cash-based approach for fixed asset management may face business failures and inefficiencies, as this method does not provide an accurate financial picture. Therefore, proper management of fixed assets in public universities demands relevant accounting skills. These assets are recorded at cost or book value, with adjustments for depreciation and amortization (Nickolas, 2022). Assets are re-evaluated when their market value falls below their book value, necessitating an accrual-based accounting system for continued relevance and growth in a competitive market. Ogundele (2014) highlighted essential accounting skills such as asset impairment testing and the straight-line depreciation method. Iheanacho (2014) added that accurate financial reporting requires knowledge of depreciation and asset assessment. This study, therefore, explores the use of various accounting skills including depreciation methods, asset valuation, and impairment testing techniques along with relevant software, to improve fixed asset management in public universities in Bayelsa State. In Pac and Abdulkarim (2016) it was postulated that the innovation that introduced information and technology into the business environment has altered the regime of office tasks and operations. It therefore follows that the use of software and applications, is changing how these conventional accounting skills are currently applied. Therefore, this study focused on depreciation methods and asset valuation and impairment testing techniques.

Depreciation methods are accounting techniques used to allocate the cost of a fixed asset over its useful life, reflecting its gradual decrease in value due to usage, wear and tear, or obsolescence (Hornngren et al., 2013). Common methods include straight-line, declining balance, and units of production, each providing a different approach to expense recognition (Kieso et al., 2019). According to Adam (2024), depreciation methods are accounting techniques used to allocate the expense of an asset over its useful life. In other words, these methods track the gradual reduction in an asset's value due to factors like age, wear and tear, or obsolescence. By accounting for any expected residual value, depreciation methods distribute an asset's cost over its useful life, matching the asset's usage with its operating costs (Weygandt, et al, 2019). This practice ensures that financial statements accurately reflect the asset's value and offers a clearer view of an institution's financial performance, particularly in managing non-current assets in public universities, while also playing a crucial role in demonstrating a company's profitability and financial health by appropriately allocating the costs associated with asset use (Kieso, et al, 2019). Depreciation methods are integral to asset valuation as they determine the allocation of an

asset's cost over time, influencing its current book value and thus impacting overall financial assessments and reporting.

Asset valuation is the process of determining the worth of an asset using various methods such as market value, income approach, or cost approach, to ensure accurate financial reporting and decision-making (Penman, 2012). Impairment testing involves evaluating assets to determine if their carrying amount exceeds their recoverable amount, thereby requiring a write-down to reflect their true value, as outlined by IAS 36 (International Accounting Standards Board, 2021). Assets valuation and impairment testing techniques in accounting are crucial for accurately reflecting an entity's financial condition. These procedures help determine an asset's fair value and identify any significant reductions in its worth. Proper asset valuation enables managers to grasp the true value of their assets (Olaniran & Onakoya, 2020). Moreover, it allows business managers and owners to perform analyses and make decisions that are beneficial for investors. The process of estimating an asset's value and recording it on the balance sheet is known as the asset valuation procedure. Different valuation methods include historical cost (the acquisition cost), fair value (the current valuation of the asset), replacement cost (the cost to replace the asset at present), and net realizable value (historical cost minus accumulated depreciation) (Aliyu, 2020). The accuracy of asset valuation and impairment testing techniques can be influenced by the gender of accountants in public universities in Bayelsa State, as diverse perspectives may impact the approach and thoroughness of financial assessments. This is the rationale for which gender is considered an important variable for this study.

Gender refers to the social and cultural distinctions between male and female identities, roles, and expectations within a society. It involves a range of characteristics, behaviours, and attributes that are culturally associated with being male or female. Gender can influence professional practices and perspectives, including how individuals approach tasks such as asset valuation and impairment testing. In public universities in Bayelsa State, the gender of accountants might affect their methods and rigor in financial assessments, potentially leading to variations in the accuracy and outcomes of these evaluations. Therefore, this study examined the utilization of accounting skills for fixed assets management in public universities in Bayelsa State.

Statement of the Problem

The effective management of fixed assets in public universities is crucial for ensuring optimal utilization and long-term sustainability of these resources. However, there are growing concerns about the ineffectiveness and inefficiencies in the tracking, valuation, and maintenance of fixed assets in public universities in Bayelsa State. Despite the importance of accounting skills in fixed assets management, many universities appear to lack adequately trained personnel in this area. As a result, issues such as underreporting, mismanagement, and poor decision-making have become prevalent, leading to financial losses and diminished asset value over time. Undoubtedly, if these evaluations are not carried out, assets may continue to be reported at inflated values that do not accurately represent their true economic worth (Gibson, 2017). Additionally, the absence of a standardized accounting framework for fixed assets often complicates the process of auditing and regulatory compliance. This problem is further exacerbated by limited access to modern accounting tools and technologies that could streamline asset management processes. Consequently, public universities in Bayelsa State are unable to fully harness the benefits of effective fixed asset management, leading to operational inefficiencies. The persistent underutilization of accounting skills in this context raises questions about the adequacy of current

training and capacity-building programmes for university accountants. Addressing this gap is critical for improving the financial health and asset sustainability of these institutions. Therefore, this study examined the extent to which accounting skills are being utilized for fixed asset management in public universities in Bayelsa State, with particular reference to depreciation methods, and asset valuation and impairment testing techniques.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the utilization of accounting skills for fixed assets management in public universities in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. determine the utilization of depreciation methods for fixed assets management in public universities in Bayelsa State.
2. determine the utilization of asset valuation and impairment testing techniques for fixed assets management in public universities in Bayelsa State

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent are depreciation methods utilized for fixed assets management in public universities in Bayelsa State?
2. To what extents are assets valuation and impairment testing techniques utilized for fixed assets management in public universities in Bayelsa State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at a significant level of 0.05.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female accountants regarding the extent of utilization of depreciation methods for fixed assets management in public universities in Bayelsa State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female accountants regarding the extent of utilization of assets valuation and impairment testing techniques for fixed assets management in public universities in Bayelsa State.

Method

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. Descriptive survey is a study which aim at collecting data on, and describing in a systematic manner, the characteristics, features or facts about a given population (B.G. Nworgu, 2006). The population for the study comprised 102 (37 males and 65 female accountants) in public universities. There was no sampling because of the population's manageable size. The instrument used for data collection was a Google form structured questionnaire developed by the researcher titled "Utilization of Accounting Skills for Fixed Assets Management Questionnaire (UASFAMQ)". The instrument was validated by three research specialists. The reliability estimate was computed using Cronbach Alpha statistic which yielded 0.78 and 0.81 for clusters 1 and 2 with a reliability index of 0.80 making the instrument reliable. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the null hypotheses were tested using t-test statistic at 0.05 level of significance. In rating the mean, each response option had a numerical value based on real limit of numbers: Very High Extent (VHE) = 3.50-4.00; High Extent (HE) = 2.50-3.49; Low Extent (LE) = 1.50-2.49 and Very Low Extent (VLE) = 0.00-1.49. The interpretation of the test of hypotheses was based on the significance (sig.)

values from the SPSS output. The null hypotheses were not rejected when the probability values are greater than 0.05, but rejected when the probability values are less than 0.05.

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent are depreciation methods utilized for fixed assets management in public universities in Bayelsa State?

Table 1: Responses on the extent of utilization of depreciation methods for fixed assets management in public universities in Bayelsa State

S/N	ITEMS	\bar{X}	SD	RM	\bar{X}	SD	RM
		Males			Females		
1	How effectively do your current depreciation methods address the rapid technological changes in your institution?	1.90	1.25	LE	2.08	1.20	LE
2	How often do you review and revise your depreciation policies to align with global best practices?	2.30	1.14	LE	1.85	1.73	LE
3	To what degree does your institution utilize analytics to enhance decision-making related to assets depreciation?	2.17	1.18	LE	2.15	1.17	LE
4	To what extent do your innovative depreciation contribute to cost savings in your fixed asset management?	2.17	1.18	LE	2.31	1.14	LE
5	To what extent does your institution consistently apply the selected depreciation methods across all fixed assets?	2.27	1.14	LE	2.15	1.17	LE
6	How effectively does your institution track the performance and accuracy of the applied depreciation methods?	1.87	1.72	LE	1.92	1.26	LE
7	To what extent do the depreciation methods in use accurately reflect the actual physical deterioration of assets?	2.33	1.14	LE	1.69	1.14	LE
8	How thoroughly are the chosen depreciation methods documented and communicated within your institution?	2.23	1.15	LE	2.15	1.38	LE
9	To what extent does your institution comply with accounting standards and regulations when applying depreciation methods?	1.97	1.24	LE	2.00	1.22	LE
10	To what extent does depreciation data guide decision-making for the asset management and replacement strategies?	2.30	1.14	LE	2.23	1.15	LE
Grand Mean & Standard Deviation		2.15	1.23	LE	2.05	1.26	LE

The table presents data on the extent of utilization of depreciation methods for fixed assets management in public universities in Bayelsa State, with responses categorized by gender. Both male and female respondents indicate a low extent (LE) of effectiveness in various aspects of

depreciation methods, as evidenced by their average ratings (means) and standard deviations. For instance, both genders reported limited effectiveness in addressing technological changes and revising depreciation policies, with means consistently below 2.5. The grand means for males (2.15) and females (2.05) further support this finding, reflecting a general consensus on the underutilization of depreciation methods across the board.

Research Question 2: To what extent are assets valuation and impairment testing techniques utilized for fixed assets management in public universities in Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Responses on the extent of utilization of assets valuation and impairment testing techniques for fixed assets management in public universities in Bayelsa State

SN	ITEMS	\bar{X}	SD	RM	\bar{X}	SD	RM
		Males			Females		
11	How extensively does your institution apply impairment testing procedures to assess the value of fixed assets?	2.13	1.18	LE	1.92	1.26	LE
12	To what extent are asset valuation and impairment methods aligned with industry standards and best practices in your institution?	2.40	1.12	LE	2.15	1.17	LE
13	To what extent does your institution ensure that valuation and impairment testing are conducted in compliance with relevant accounting standards?	2.07	1.20	LE	2.31	1.14	LE
14	How thoroughly are the results of asset valuation and impairment testing documented and communicated within your institution?	1.87	1.72	LE	2.62	1.12	LE
15	To what extent do valuation techniques used reflect the current market conditions and asset performance?	2.17	1.18	LE	2.00	1.22	LE
16	To what extent does your institution incorporate input from external appraisers or valuation experts in asset valuation?	2.50	1.12	LE	1.92	1.26	LE
17	How effectively does your institution track changes in asset values and their impact on financial statements?	2.23	1.15	LE	2.54	1.12	LE
18	To what extent are impairment indicators monitored and assessed regularly to ensure timely testing of fixed assets?	2.07	1.20	LE	2.15	1.38	LE
19	How effectively does your institution address discrepancies between asset book values and market values during impairment testing?	2.40	1.12	LE	2.08	1.20	LE
20	How well does your institution train staff involved in asset valuation and impairment testing on best practices and standards?	2.23	1.20	LE	2.08	1.20	LE
Grand Mean & Standard Deviation		2.21	1.22	LE	2.18	1.21	LE

The table illustrates the extent of utilization of asset valuation and impairment testing techniques in public universities in Bayelsa State, with responses from both male and female participants showing a low extent (LE) of application. Both groups reported limited use of impairment testing procedures and alignment with industry standards, indicating that these techniques are not effectively integrated into asset management practices. The results also show that documentation and communication of valuation outcomes are less thorough, with females reporting slightly higher engagement in some areas such as tracking changes in asset values. Overall, the grand means for

males (2.21) and females (2.18) reflect a general consensus that asset valuation and impairment testing techniques are underutilized, which may affect the accuracy and effectiveness of fixed asset management in these institutions.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female accountants regarding the extent of utilization of depreciation methods for fixed assets management in public universities in Bayelsa State.

Table 3: t-test analysis on the mean scores of male and female accountants regarding the extent of utilization of depreciation methods for fixed assets management in public universities

Group	N	\bar{X}	SD	DF	P-value	Decision
Male	37	2.15	1.23	100	.058	H ₀₁ not rejected
Female	65	2.05	1.26			

The table presents a t-test analysis comparing the mean scores of male and female accountants on the extent of utilization of depreciation methods for fixed assets management in public universities in Bayelsa State. The male accountants had a mean score of 2.15 with a standard deviation of 1.23, while the female accountants had a mean score of 2.05 with a standard deviation of 1.26. With a p-value of 0.058, which is greater than the significance level, the null hypothesis (**H₀₁**) is not rejected, indicating no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female accountants. Therefore, gender does not significantly influence the utilization of depreciation methods for fixed assets management in this context.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female accountants regarding the extent of utilization of assets valuation and impairment testing techniques for fixed assets management in public universities in Bayelsa State.

Table 4: t-test analysis on the mean scores of male and female accountants regarding the extent of utilization of assets valuation and impairment testing techniques for fixed assets management in public universities

Group	N	\bar{X}	SD	DF	P-value	Decision
Male	37	2.21	1.22	100	.063	H ₀₂ not rejected
Female	65	2.18	1.21			

The table shows a t-test analysis comparing the mean responses of male and female accountants regarding the extent of utilization of assets valuation and impairment testing techniques for fixed assets management in public universities in Bayelsa State. The mean score for male accountants is 2.21 with a standard deviation of 1.22, while female accountants have a mean score of 2.18 with a standard deviation of 1.21. With a p-value of 0.063, which is greater than the significance level, the null hypothesis (**H₀₂**) is not rejected. This indicates there is no significant difference between

male and female accountants in the utilization of assets valuation and impairment testing techniques.

Discussion of Findings

The findings indicate that the depreciation method, which is crucial for assessing the wear and tear of fixed assets over time, was applied minimally in public universities for managing their assets. This underutilization can lead to inaccurate financial reporting, as the real value of assets is not properly reflected in the institutions' financial statements. As a result, this may hinder effective decision-making related to asset replacement, budgeting, and overall resource management within the universities.

The findings align with the views of Jones and Pendlebury (2010), who argue that the inadequate application of depreciation methods can lead to significant misrepresentation of asset values in financial statements, impairing accurate financial reporting. Similarly, Ndaruhutse and Plimmer (2012) emphasize that the failure to properly account for asset depreciation hampers decision-making processes related to asset replacement and resource allocation in educational institutions. Consequently, the underutilization of depreciation methods in public universities could undermine the institutions' financial transparency and long-term sustainability.

The findings show that asset valuation and impairment testing techniques, which are vital for determining the current market value and condition of fixed assets, were employed to a limited extent in public universities. This low utilization may result in outdated or inaccurate asset values being reported, potentially affecting financial transparency and resource allocation decisions. Consequently, universities may face challenges in managing their assets efficiently, leading to a lack of timely interventions for asset renewal or disposal.

The findings are supported by Biddle, Bowen, and Wallace (2015), who highlight that the underutilization of asset valuation and impairment testing techniques can result in the misstatement of asset values, negatively impacting financial transparency. Similarly, Rees and Gill (2016) argue that limited use of these techniques hampers accurate financial reporting, leading to inefficient resource allocation and decision-making. As a result, universities may face difficulties in effectively managing their assets, delaying critical actions such as asset renewal or disposal.

Conclusion

The study revealed that depreciation methods, asset valuation, and impairment testing techniques are underutilized in the management of fixed assets in public universities. This low level of utilization has implications for the accuracy and transparency of financial reporting in these institutions. It was unraveled that there was no staff training program, no policy in place to review and revise depreciation, no assets valuation and impairment testing to align with global best practices for the practitioners to enhance effectiveness and efficiency, no proper documentation of depreciation among others. Effective fixed asset management is essential for maintaining the long-term value and operational efficiency of university resources. Addressing these gaps requires targeted interventions such as training, policy revisions, and the integration of technology. Therefore, it is critical for public universities to adopt best practices in asset management to enhance their financial sustainability and accountability.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommended that:

1. University management should organize regular training and capacity-building workshops for asset managers and finance officers in public universities to enhance their knowledge and skills in the use of modern depreciation methods, asset valuation, and impairment testing techniques. This will improve the accuracy of fixed asset management and financial reporting in the institutions.
2. Public universities should adopt and implement standardized asset management policies that mandate the use of appropriate depreciation methods and asset impairment testing procedures. This can be achieved by aligning institutional policies with international financial reporting standards (IFRS) to ensure consistency and transparency in fixed asset management.
3. Public universities should invest in advanced asset management software that automates depreciation calculations, asset valuation, and impairment testing. Such systems will help in keeping accurate records, providing real-time data on asset conditions, and ensuring the efficient management of fixed assets across the institution.
4. Institutional management should collaborate with government to create the path and make adequate funds available for acquisition of requisite facilities to facilitate effective implementation and utilization of the novel idea.
5. There is need to improve the syllabus of tertiary institutions to accommodate many globally acceptable and applicable innovations in the accounting sector to improve accounting operations

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